

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE PERCEPTION OF CRICKETING PLAYERS AND OFFICIALS INTO THE QUOTA POLICY ON CRICKET

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Abstract

South Africa's racially divided past has led to the institution of various remedial measures across all segments of life, whereby the imbalances of the past are being addressed. Of all the remedial measures employed, the quota policy in sport which is an extension of affirmative action, has been a source of debate and contention. The cricket authorities have struggled to achieve transformation targets but should not shoulder the burden of this under-achievement alone. Government has not provided the necessary infrastructure and facilities at schools to facilitate the development and transformation of cricket. This brings into question the effectiveness of the management and administration of the quota policy in cricket. The results of the quantitative study have shown that the respondents to the survey are discontented with the effectiveness of the management and administration of the quota policy. Furthermore, the respondents believed that the quota policy was unnecessary and responsible for players leaving the country. The authors recommend that the provision of facilities and infrastructure at schools become a high priority in order to stimulate participation in cricket and facilitate the development of cricketers at grassroots level. Furthermore, a synergistic relationship between cricket federations and schools must be fostered.

Keywords: Cricket Transformation; Affirmative Action Quotas; Sports Administration.

Introduction

Cricket South Africa (CSA) has recently reintroduced racial quotas in the selection of representative cricket teams, stipulating that the national team field a minimum average of 54% black cricketers, of which must comprise a minimum average of 18% black African cricketers over the season. The management and administration of these quotas are resonant with similar measures implemented in the early years post-apartheid. Government is demanding quotas as a result of unmet transformation targets which were agreed to by all stakeholders in the sport.

The quota system has been cited as a primary reason for young cricketers leaving South Africa to pursue cricketing careers overseas or leaving the sport entirely. The South African cricket fraternity is divided on the issue of quotas. The legality of the quota policy has been challenged and is alleged to contravene the Employment Equity Act, considering that players at franchise and national level are contractually employed.

Considering the various perspectives, the quota policy in cricket is commonly viewed as contentious and therefore this study will aim to evaluate the management and administration of the quota policy whilst arriving at recommendations for the implementation of changes as required.

Background to the Study

South Africa's history of racial segregation in all aspects of life under the auspices of apartheid has created imbalances in society that justifiably requires redress.

Since the initial introduction of racial quotas in cricket, numerous young white cricketers have left South Africa to ply their trade in England, New Zealand and some non-test cricketing nations. The most notable of these is Kevin Pietersen of England who openly cited his reason for leaving South African cricket as racial quotas (Desai, 2016). In an interview with ESPN Cricinfo in 2006, Pietersen declared:

"I was dropped because the quota system was brought into South African cricket to positively discriminate in favour of 'players of colour' and to fast-track the racial integration of cricket in the country" (ESPN Cricinfo, 2006)".

The racial quota system, as employed by CSA for the selection of representative cricket teams, has resulted in cricketers leaving the country and the sport, and questioning the necessity of racial quotas.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the management and administration of the racial quota policy, as employed by CSA, on cricket in KwaZulu-Natal (KZN), as experienced by the various stakeholders of the sport.

Literature Review

It is essential to understand the fundamentals of racially based policies in South Africa and South African cricket, from governments' position to academia and the stakeholders of the sport. It serves to validate governments' involvement in prescribing policy to sports federations. In order to get a clear insight into the need for transformation of cricket in South Africa, one has to touch on the history of apartheid cricket and examine the political and social stimuli involved in the sport's transformation and restructuring initiatives.

The review progresses onto an overview of affirmative action and the interpretations thereof in a South African context. The White Paper on Sport and Recreation of 2013, The National Sports and Recreation Amendment Bill of 2006, The Employment Equity Act No. 55 of 1998 and CSAs Transformation Charter are examined to support discussion and create context.

Lastly, opinions from stakeholders and media and limited studies around the broader aspects of transformation in cricket are explored.

Apartheid Cricket

Apartheid is an Afrikaans word which loosely translated into English means 'separateness' or literally 'apart-hood' and is "a rigid former policy of segregating and economically and politically oppressing the non-white population" (Oxford English Dictionary, 2007:35). During the years of apartheid in South Africa, the government's policy of separate development extended not only to the creation of homelands for black people, but a separation of race groups in all aspects of daily life, including the cricket fields.

Cricket in Victorian England was viewed as "a particularly useful way of morally disciplining colonials and inculcating ideals of stamina, manliness and vigour into lazy and effete colonials" (Vahed *et al.*, 2006:66). Nauright (1997:26-27) as cited in Vahed *et al.* (2006:66) and Odendaal (2010) state that even though all South Africans played cricket, only whites could be selected to officially represent South Africa thus compelling the Indians, Coloureds and Africans to create separate cricket structures and federations. Whilst black cricket and black cricketers were marginalised in South Africa since the game was introduced by the English, Prime Minister John Vorster's refusal to accept Basil D'Oliveira as a member of the South African cricket team started the cricketing world's boycott of South African cricket (Desai, 2016:2; Osborne, 2004:114). During the time that South Africa was isolated from competing on the world stage, white cricket still flourished within the country and the yearning for international competition was partially assuaged with unsanctioned rebel tours by Australia, West Indies and England (Odendaal, 2010). The justification for these rebel tours was that it would generate much needed income to be used in the development of cricket in black townships (Desai, 2016:4). Even then, black cricketers were excluded from selection to the South African team.

The International Cricket Council (ICC) of which South Africa is a member, condemns racism of any form in its Anti-Racism Policy, stating that, "The ICC and all of its Members should:

- a) Not at any time offend, insult, humiliate, intimidate, threaten, disparage, vilify or unlawfully discriminate between persons based on their race, religion, culture, colour, descent, and/or national or ethnic origin;
- b) Adopt appropriate policies that it is clear to all employees, officials, commercial partners and other participants and stakeholders that inappropriate Racist Conduct (including in any public statements) will not be tolerated by the ICC or by the Member;" (International Cricket Council, 2012:1).

If the ICC policy on Anti-Racism is strictly adhered to, then CSA must be in contravention of this policy with the implementation of a racial quota policy.

Government Intervention in Sport

Naidoo (2008) attempts to find justification in government's interference in sport prompted by public outcry through his article on the Theoretical Foundations of Sport Administration. Naidoo (2008) establishes the synergistic relationship between public administration and sports administration.

Fox, Schwella and Wissink (1991:2) as cited in Naidoo (2008:31) define public administration as:

“...that system of structures and processes operating within a particular society as the environment, with the objective of facilitating the formulation of appropriate governmental policies and the effective and efficient execution of the formulated policies”.

Naidoo (2008) provides a thoroughly researched summation that weaves the various aspects of public administration with sport administration, thus concluding that the Minister of Sport, guided by the National Sports and Recreation Amendment Act of 2007, “is duty bound to ensure that sport federations are accountable”.

The 2013 White Paper on Sport and Recreation clearly states that the racial composition of national sports teams should not be prescribed and neither must National Sports Federations be prescribed to on the selection of teams. The White Paper on Sport and Recreation (2013) further advocates merit selection of sports teams and advises implementation of transformation at school and youth levels. Racial quotas prescribed by the Minister of Sport therefore must be in contravention of the policy directives outlined in the White Paper on Sport and Recreation (2013). Threats by the Minister of Sport to withdraw the national colours, block sponsorship and withdraw funding and support of federations that come across as “hostile to transformation” also contravene the directives of the White Paper (Du Preez, 2014).

Upon receiving advice from the National Sport and Recreation Indaba held in November 2011, the Minister of Sport and Recreation appointed the Eminent Persons Group (EPG) to provide “...strategic policy advice on the status of transformation...on the implementation of the Transformation Charter and its score-card...” (EPG Transformation Status Report, 2014/15:iv).

The new Minister of Sport and Recreation, Thembelani Nxesi has listed the “...acceleration of transformation and revival of school sport...” as high priority (Mphahlele, 2017). The minister acknowledges awaiting the EPGs latest report and further acknowledges that the EPG report has become “...a highly credible and well researched document...” and that government “...will have to engage on its findings” (Mphahlele, 2017). The minister committed to giving urgent attention to school sport and youth development with the objective of creating a larger talent pool for national selection (Mphahlele, 2017). The minister further acknowledged that the country is facing a “...looming crisis of sustainability for sport as a whole if we do not address the challenges in school sport” whilst also acknowledging that some sport codes exercise an unsustainable dependence on the ex-Model C and private schooling system as the talent identification pipeline (Mphahlele, 2017).

Haroon Lorgat and Norman Arendse, both of CSA, acknowledged that government's demands for better representation of black players in cricket teams was not being backed up by government investment into township schools in order to facilitate grassroots development (Desai, 2010:183-184). The avenue for development of black cricketers since unification has been “white schools” with most of South Africa's black representatives in national cricket teams having been groomed and nurtured at elite schools (Desai, 2010:183). With the exception of Mfuneko Ngam and Thandi Tshabalala, no other black African cricketer has achieved national honours after being born, bred and schooled in a township (Young, 2016). Unequal development at grassroots level, particularly in township schools has still not been addressed adequately by government. The need for specialist equipment, coaching and facilities has been the main prohibitive factors stifling the development of amateur social cricketers to consummate professionals (Desai, 2010).

Mnyanda (2016) reports that South Africa's minister of sport declared that he will not “beg for racial transformation”, but will force sports bodies to fulfil prescribed racial quotas. Forcing sports federations to fulfil quotas will naturally force the federations to attract players of colour with the hope of developing them to a professional level. The enforcement of quotas will also mean that some unfortunate white player who was most likely born in the “New South Africa” will not receive the same attention and opportunities at being selected. Mnyanda (2016) highlights the history of deliberate talent suppression and rightly so, whilst condoning quotas as a “necessary and overdue” action. However, this stance also condones reverse discrimination and talent suppression. Future generations will constantly attempt to right the wrongs of the past, depending on where the power lies politically.

Affirmative Action

Cohen and Sterba (2003) argue the morality and legality of affirmative action in an American context, whilst internationally relevant. Cohen contends that preferential treatment contravenes the “plain language” of the Civil Rights Act and the constitution of the United States (Cohen & Sterba, 2003:48). Sterba asserts that ‘the act allows for

preferences as a means to correct for violations of the act” (Cohen & Sterba, 2003:205). Sterba explains outreach affirmative action as follows:

“All reasonable steps must be taken to ensure that qualified minority and women candidates have available to them the same educational and job opportunities that are available to non-minority or male candidates” (Cohen & Sterba, 2003:203)”.

This is the intention of affirmative action in the South African context as well and indeed in the South African cricket context albeit with reference to the majority of South African people. The operative word in Sterba’s statement is qualified (Cohen & Sterba, 2003:203). South Africans have witnessed the business sector in South Africa applying affirmative action flagrantly based on colour only, with little or no regard to qualification as in the case of the South African Airways chairperson and various other state owned and private enterprises. The question arises as to what qualifies a cricketer for selection to a representative team. Merely possessing the correct equipment simply cannot be enough. However, possessing the necessary skills set which positively differentiates the cricketer from the rest of the contenders for that place in the team should be the qualifying criteria. In the event of both a white player and a black player being suitably skilled for a particular place in the team, the place must be given to the black player. The ideal shrouded within a racial quota policy is undeniably egalitarian. CSA is applying an affirmative action policy through its racial quota policy. CSA must ensure that the interpretation and implementation of the racial quota policy delivers the intended results.

Thomen (2008:33) argues the merits and demerits of compensating sports people of colour that were “directly or indirectly disadvantaged by apartheid”. Measures of this nature could bring about discrimination wherein the disadvantaged roles become reversed. Thomen (2008:33) seeks to highlight how the adverse effects of such policies tend to negate any positives that may arise from its implementation. Thomen (2008:9) further suggests that affirmative action has multiple meanings, depending on who one is speaking to and summarises it as follows:

“To some people it might mean economic empowerment and the triumph of justice; to others it might mean a devaluation of their ability to compete in a meritocratic system or an unfair infringement on their right to be treated equally along with everyone else” (Thomen, 2008:9)”.

Examined from any perspective, affirmative action, whether implemented as a remedy for past injustices, current shortcomings or as a beacon of hope for the future, will invariably take some sort of racial slant, where one race group benefits over another.

Employment Equity Act, (Act No. 55 of 1998)

From an employment law perspective, the idea of a quota policy in cricket is somewhat peculiar. Attorneys specialising in labour law, Coetzer and Braatvedt (2015) assert that a sports team not reflecting the demographics of its province or the country cannot be said to show the extent of transformation in South Africa let alone being representative of its populace. Coetzer and Braatvedt (2015) further support the provision of a legal framework for the implementation of measures to ensure that sports teams should comprise representative proportions from designated groups, meaning black people, women and people with disabilities.

The Employment Equity Act (EEA), No. 55 of 1998, introduced the concept of affirmative action into South Africa’s workplaces. Quotas for sports teams emerged around this time as well. The EEA provides for employers to formulate and implement an employment equity plan that will achieve “reasonable progress towards employment equity” in the workforce through various measures, including numerical targets and “preferential treatment” (Employment Equity Act, 1998). Cricketers who are contracted to play for a franchise are employed by the franchise. In terms of the EEA, these franchises may be classified as designated employers and should be required to comply through the preparation of employment equity plans (Coetzer & Braatvedt, 2015).

According to Coetzer and Braatvedt (2015), numerous cases have come before the courts for the clarification of the EEA. What has become clear since the inception of the EEA is that there is a difference between targets and quotas which amounts to the flexibility of the two mechanisms (Coetzer & Braatvedt, 2015). In the case between *Solidarity & Others vs The Department of Correctional Services & Others*, it was held by the Labour Appeal Court that “numerical targets which create an absolute bar, such as a quota, are not permitted by the EEA” (Coetzer & Braatvedt, 2015). Interpreting the court’s ruling in the cricket context simply means that if a franchise instructs team selectors to choose a team which include a predetermined number of designated group players, then that franchise will be in contravention of the EEA (Coetzer & Braatvedt, 2015). Coetzer and Braatvedt (2015) validate their claim citing the inflexibility of the rule and that it “does not take account of various factors, which may be relevant to the consideration.” It is therefore imperative that employment equity plans be reasonable and flexible because from a legal standpoint, there “is no reason why the same principles should not be applicable to sports teams and the organisations that they form part of” (Coetzer & Braatvedt, 2015).

Transformation in Cricket

The Transformation Charter for South African cricket was unveiled on 3 January 1999 following a series of vision seminars hosted by UCBSA (Cricket South Africa). Thereafter, a Transformation Monitoring Committee (TMC) was formed to ensure that the Transformation Charter was being adhered to and Provincial Monitoring Committees were responsible for regional adherence of the charter (Desai, 2016:128). Odendaal (2003:338), having also served on the TMC accuses whites of adopting a mentality opposing transformation and of lacking simple empathy by being unable to acknowledge the “negative impact of the past”. Odendaal (2003:338) further expounds his theory by pointing out that by way of that mentality, whites “somehow still feel the aggrieved party, despite having blatantly supported and benefited from apartheid”.

Since unification of cricket in South Africa, CSA has openly acknowledged the disparities that exist between cricketers of different race groups, in particular the Black African cricketer from the townships and rural areas. The CSA Transformation Philosophy and Plan (2002) highlights the need to equalise the imbalances and level the uneven playing fields created by South Africa’s historically prejudiced past.

“Our historic and moral duty is to ensure that South African cricket grows and flourishes among the truly disadvantaged of our society, with the recognition that the majority of disadvantaged people come from our Black African communities” (CSA Annual Report, 2011:5”).

The CSA Transformation Philosophy and Plan (2002) further recognises that, in the midst of previously disadvantaged cricketers, there will be individuals that, by virtue of their race or gender, will have been more disadvantaged than their fellow cricketers. Gerald Majola, then CEO of CSA, stated categorically: “Our challenge is simple: we have to produce cricket teams that win most of their matches. And we have to build cricket teams that reflect the make-up of our nation” (CSA Strategic Plan for the Future, 2002). It is clear today that Majola underestimated the enormity of the task at hand. It is also clear today that both those objectives could not be achieved simultaneously as the chasm between a winning team and a racially representative team was enormous.

Taliep (2009) spent 10 years examining the effectiveness of the cricket transformation process in firstly, increasing the representation of black cricketers and secondly, improving the performance of black cricketers at provincial level. Taliep (2009) concluded that the transformation process had realised “reasonable success” based on the higher numbers of black cricketers performing “according to standard”. Further to his research, Taliep’s (2009) statistics suggest the following:

- That the transformation initiatives of CSA may not be properly aligned with its goals;
- The statistics for performance levels of white cricketers is deteriorating;
- That research of this nature is not always considered by stakeholders in cricket when policy is being set.

Taliep’s (2009) findings are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Findings – Taliep, 2009
White batsmen had significantly higher batting averages than black Africans, but were only better than coloureds/Indians in the 2001/2002 season.
Coloureds/Indians had better batting averages than black Africans in all seasons except 2001/2002 and 2004/2005.
There was a significant improvement in the batting averages of coloureds/Indians but not of whites and black Africans over the 12 seasons.
White bowlers had significantly better bowling averages than coloured/Indian bowlers for seasons 2002/2003, 2004/2005 and 2006/2007.
There were no significant differences in the bowling averages between white and black African players and between coloured/Indian and black African players over the 12 seasons. There was a tendency towards a decreased bowling performance for coloureds/Indians, whereas there was no significant decrement in the bowling performance for whites and black Africans over the 12 seasons.
Source: Adapted from South African Journal of Sports Medicine (2009:156)

Farland and Jennings (2007:831) are more direct in their claim that black people have gravitated toward football, athletics and boxing due to the lack of necessary infrastructure required for the sport of cricket and the relative high cost

of cricket equipment. That claim is further substantiated with generalisation that black people were “excluded from sources of wealth” and from the better schools and well established clubs that fostered the sport of cricket (Farland and Jennings, 2007:831). Farland and Jennings (2007:836) further postulate that all things being equal, and if the integrity of selectors is intact, then “white racism is ultimately responsible for the fact that the national cricket team is white dominated”. It cannot be as simple as that. Consider that all things are equal, and that the selectors are simply handicapped by a very small pool of quality cricketers most of whom happen to be white, one could assume that blacks are simply not as interested in the game of cricket as whites are. Others may suggest that blacks are simply not as good as whites at the sport.

Stakeholder Perspective

According to a 2016 national survey by the South African Institute of Race Relations asking the South African public their opinion regarding merit based selection of national sports teams, 77% of all South Africans supported merit based selection of sports teams without the implementation of racial quotas (Pretorius, 2016).

Table 2: South Africans opposed to Racial Quotas in Sport

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Should South African sports teams only be selected on merit and ability and not racial quotas?	Total	Black	Coloured	Asian	White
YES	77.0%	74.2%	87.0%	94.9%	84.3%
NO	22.7%	25.5%	13.0%	5.1%	15.1%
Source: Adapted from News24 (2016)					

According to Moonda (2013) a report commissioned by CSA stated that “most black African players give up the game between the under-19 and provincial level, at an age at which, if they are not contracted, will need to find jobs”. The report also revealed that when black African players do get into the system, they are often further side lined. Only two black African players turned out in more than 80% of their franchises' games in 2012 and when they did, they bowled less overs and batted lower down than players of other races (Moonda, 2013). Statistics such as these questions the sincerity of the efforts of cricket’s management toward transformation.

According to Murray and Merrett (2004:156), in order to save the tour of Australia in 1971, Donald Bradman advised the South African cricket selectors to select two blacks in the touring team. Dik Abed and Owen Williams were selected but the South African Cricket Board of Control (SACBOC) refused to sanction the selection and both players refused to tour, with Williams stating that he refused to “be a glorified baggage master” (Murray & Merrett, 2004:156). The stand taken by Abed and Williams, albeit for a much bigger cause, is not lost on cricketers of today. Charl Langeveld, a coloured cricketer, was chosen to replace Andre Nel, a white cricketer, in a team to tour India due to the team looking “too white” and not meeting the approval of CSAs president, Norman Arendse (Arthur, 2010:114). Arthur (2010:115) reveals how despondent this selection made Langeveld feel, leading to Langeveld withdrawing from the team.

In November 2015, black African players complained to CSA about the lack of playing time on the tour to India (Molobi, 2015). It seemed at the time that CSAs first concern was that the letter was leaked to the press whilst thereafter categorising the complaint as serious enough to warrant a task team being set up under the guidance of ex-CSA president Norman Arendse (Desai, 2016). The task team found that the players were indeed treated unfairly especially in light of the fact that the fifth limited overs match was of no importance to an already decided series and offered the selectors an opportunity to field all the players who had limited or no game time during the tour (Desai, 2016: 219-220).

Steen (2013) reports that a letter sent in 2007 to Norman Arendse, then President of CSA, and his board members by Ashwell Prince and other senior players “demanded an end to artificial selection at the highest level”. Later that year, sports minister Stofile labelled quotas as window dressing, signifying a shift towards the notion that victory on the field would be a more effective form of inspiration. Minister Stofile, an avid rugby fan and exceptional player during the apartheid years, won many friends with his stand against the quota system (Greenaway, 2007).

Moonda (2016) reported on the exodus of South African cricketers and officials to mainly England and supported her article with interviews with past and present players and administrators affiliated to CSA. The players and officials requested anonymity due to the sensitive nature of the subject. One of the reasons cited for players leaving the country is money, where they are offered substantially larger contracts overseas than domestically. Another reason cited for leaving South Africa was the anxiety of selection due to aggressive transformation targets in the form of racial quotas (Moonda, 2016). Moonda (2016) also confirms through a current senior national player that several younger white players are

seeking opportunities in the United Kingdom citing the "...several variables in South African cricket and the lack of opportunity" as reasons for leaving. Another former player identifies the lack of transparency around the implementation of the quota policy rather than the policy itself as a cause for player exodus (Moonda, 2016).

The exodus of young white cricketers to England, Australia, New Zealand, Scotland, Ireland and Netherlands indicates a crisis that is developing in South African cricket. Kevin Pietersen is a notable example as he cited the quota system as his motivation for pursuing a cricketering career in England. However, the reasoning of the less prominent expat cricketer must also be considered.

Tony Irish, the CEO of the South African Cricket Association as cited in Louw (2014) reported that matters had become intolerable amongst players since racial quotas were introduced:

"The players feel that as soon as a racial number is set for selection of the team (whether or not one calls this a quota or a target) it leads to a divisive dynamic within the team, and it is also degrading to the players of colour who should be there on merit, yet are labelled a quota/target player" (Louw, 2014)".

With the exception of Kevin Pietersen's comments and Tony Irish's assertion, not much has been publicly documented about the players' feelings toward the racial quota system. Understandably, players are bound by contracts that prevent them from speaking out against their employers and for fear of reprisal.

Hartman (2004) in writing the biography of Ali Bacher, highlights Bacher's connectedness with all quarters of the cricketering fraternity and government, whilst unwittingly exposing Bacher's double standards. Bacher issued a media statement against South Africa fielding an all-white team but is reported in a Sunday newspaper adding that standards must not be compromised and that the UCBSA was "opposed to quotas at national level" Hartman (2004:327). Bacher went further to say that the UCBSA would be "unhappy if government legislation interfered in the running of our sport", but hastened to add that South Africa needed a "national cricket team of colour" (Hartman, 2004:327). Bacher has been hailed as the voice, face and hero of South African cricket by many stakeholders in cricket, but Desai (2016:60-72) exposes him as a manipulative martyr for white cricket under the guise of an agent for transformation and development.

One of Gerald Majola's first acts as CEO in the year 2000 was to scrap quotas for the adoption of transformation targets and guidelines (Nyoka, 2015:55). At that time Mtutuzeli Nyoka, the then president of the Gauteng Cricket Board and one of the leading voices for the Africanisation of cricket was taken aback by the changes as he believed that the "quota policy was the sharpest point of the affirmative action policy" and that to scrap it was "idiotic" (Desai, 2016:184). Majola took everyone by surprise when he openly criticised both the quota policy and affirmative action, prompting the minister of sport, Nonde Balfour to set up a commission of inquiry which resulted in both criticism and praise for UCBSA (Desai, 2016:184). Majola's stand against government interference was applauded and he looked as though he was not prepared to succumb to pressure from the ministry of sport. Surprisingly though, Majola went as far as opposing Norman Arendse and the selectors who were pushing the transformation agenda to side with coach Mickey Arthur on various selection issues that were not favourable to transformation (Desai, 2016:188).

Manthorpe (2015) interviewed various stakeholders of South African cricket in April 2015 on the back of CSAs announcement that the racial quota was increased to six players of colour of which three must be black African. Coaches and administrators found that they had no room to manoeuvre when the quota was five players of colour and would find it more difficult to negotiate the increased quota. Coaches and administrators felt intimidated by CSAs aggressive stand on selection particularly since CEOs of franchises unable to meet the quotas were required to explain themselves to a CSA committee at the CEOs personal expense (Manthorpe, 2015). This hardened, aggressive stance stemmed from franchises abusing the system.

CSAs high performance director, Corrie van Zyl, refuted arguments by franchises that there simply were not enough blacks playing the game using statistics he had garnered himself proving that there indeed was an increasing number of black players available for selection (Manthorpe, 2015). Haroon Lorgat, CEO of CSA implored his fellow administrators to "...admit that we have simply not done enough to uncover talent that surely exists in our country" (Manthorpe, 2015). In an interview with Macpherson (2016) regarding the exodus of South African cricketers to England, Lorgat was less forgiving of expat cricketers who allude to the racial quota policy and transformation targets as their reasons for departure claiming those players were "...looking for a soft excuse..." and that they were not prepared to fight for selection into the representative cricket teams. Lorgat ended that interview emphatically stating that "We only select the best as was evident in our recent successes against Australia. You don't whitewash Australia or beat them seven times in a row without choosing your best" (Macpherson, 2016). Based on Lorgat's assertions one may argue that the South African cricket team is selected purely on merit and that the racial quota policy is unnecessary.

Findings from the Study

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the management and administration of the racial quota policy in KZN cricket.

The responses to the research questions indicated the following:

- That the management and administration of the racial quota policy in KZN cricket is not effective. Respondents displayed a good understanding of the selection policies and the motivation for such policies. However, the respondents felt that the selection policy was not applied with consistency in KZN and that the selection policy discriminated against certain race groups.
- That the racial quota policy does influence cricketers to seek opportunities abroad and / or leave the game prematurely.
- That the racial quota policy is not necessary in South African cricket. Whilst the first two research questions were answered unequivocally, the responses to the third research question were not as overwhelmingly emphatic. The statistical analysis indicated a racial bias whereby most black Africans were in favour of the quota policy whilst Indians were equally divided and Whites and Coloureds were not in favour of the quota policy. The racial bias was also consistent with a survey conducted by the South African Institute of Race Relations where the majority of South Africans were not in favour of the racial quota policy but almost 25% of black Africans were in favour and understandably so (Pretorius, 2016). The political past of South Africa can only be understood by the South Africans who lived through it. People process their experiences differently and while some choose to move on, others cannot and some will not, for various reasons.

The literature review has shown that due to a poor school sport structure in South Africa as a whole, transformation targets cannot be met. The management and administration of the quota policy will remain contentious as long as the grassroots development of the sport is neglected. Furthermore, government's expectations of the sport, in the absence of a synergistic relationship between the Departments of Sport and Recreation and Basic Education or the necessary investment in infrastructure and facilities, are untenable. The quota policy will continue to appear as a superficial measure to create representivity.

Conclusion

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the management and administration of the quota policy on cricket in KZN and was achieved. The study has shown that the quota policy in cricket is indeed contentious. One must be cognisant that the quota policy has been imposed on cricket authorities by other senior cricket authorities and government. Government has adopted a "top / down" approach which will not succeed whilst the necessary infrastructure and facilities have not been provided at the most elementary levels, namely schools where talent is nurtured. In light of this, the administrators of cricket in KZN should not bear the full brunt for the effects of the much maligned quota policy in the absence of necessary and essential structures. Given the failings of the Department of Education and of the Department of Sport to provide suitable cricket facilities and equipment at previously disadvantaged schools, some of the blame for so few Black players at the top level in cricket should be shouldered by the relevant government departments and not only at cricket's governing bodies.

The quota policy in cricket and other sports is viewed negatively by most South Africans. Some black African people are in favour of quotas as the scars of apartheid run deeper amongst black Africans than other South Africans. The quota policy comes with its own set of problems and most notable of all, in the future, may be termed the scars of democracy.

Whilst ensuring that black people in South Africa are given adequate opportunity to be selected to representative cricket teams, the quota policy also ensures that other South Africans, particularly whites who have no lived experience of apartheid and segregation, are discriminated against. This is more so for the younger generation born post 1994 and some would argue even people born as far back as 1990. Arguments have been made for positive discrimination but discrimination in any form, especially against children and young adults must not be seen as a solution to historical injustices.

In conclusion, this research has highlighted imbalances of the past and has explored the issue of racial quotas in cricket in South Africa and the effect they have on players and on cricket. Whilst CSA admits that it could do more to address the topic, a core area where more needs to be done to attract and develop players is at school level and as most schools are state run, it is imperative that the state plays its part in developing Black talent and in fact all talent. One can but hope that the proverbial playing fields will be levelled in a manner in which the previously disadvantaged races will be given better facilities to develop their talents and that it will be done so as to create equal opportunity for all in cricket and other sports.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Lack of facilities at schools – Possibly the most critical problem in the entire transformation agenda. The provision of facilities at schools is the responsibility of the government. The Department of Sport and

Recreation and the Department of Basic Education must collaborate and prioritise the provision of sport facilities at schools. Only once this is accomplished can the cricket federations be expected to provide the development component that impact on the quota policy.

- Lack of participation at schools - As a basis for a way forward, it is imperative that a well aligned and cooperative sport federation structure comprising national, local and provincial government and the cricket federation develops a plan for increased intra and inter-school participation in cricket.
- There must be clear sport policies at schools that link to the relative sports federation structures. This will ensure continuity in the development of players from the school system to the federation system. A synergistic relationship between schools and cricket federations will provide the structure that is severely lacking. Furthermore, a strong relationship between schools and cricket federations can also ensure that opportunities become available for those talented cricketers who want to pursue a career in sport.
- CSA and its affiliates need to educate all their stakeholders, particularly players, on the selection policies and various criteria involved in selection. The quota policy is viewed in a negative light and transparency will alleviate negative perceptions whilst compelling the federations to apply the policies with consistency.
- KZNCU should formulate a clear development and academy system that is transparent to the sporting public thereby allowing the public to understand how selection takes place and what the requirements are of players to warrant selection.
- In terms of the study and EPG findings linked to the selection policies, it is recommended that CSA and its affiliates urgently review the quota policy. There is a need for a national indaba of all stakeholders to find an alternative to the quota policy, one which will ensure that the disadvantages of the past are recognised and that the imbalances which have arisen are addressed.

References

- [1] Arthur, M. 2010. *Taking The Mickey: The Inside Story*. Johannesburg: Jonathan Ball.
- [2] Coetzer, N. and Braatvedt, N. 2015. An Employment Law Perspective of Quotas on Sports. <https://mg.co.za/article/2015-09-18-an-employment-law-perspective-of-quotas-on-sports> Date of access: 15 February 2017.
- [3] Cohen, C. and Sterba, J.P. 2003. *Affirmative Action and Racial Preference: A Debate*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [4] Cricket South Africa: CSA Strategic Plan for the Future, Johannesburg. 2002. <http://cricket.co.za/item/332/Corporate-Information> Date of access: 8 August 2016.
- [5] Cricket South Africa: CSA Annual Report, Johannesburg. 2011. <http://ipublish.cc/wp/csa/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2014/12/2010-2011-CSA-Annual-Report-and-Financial-Statement.pdf> Date of Access: 8 August 2016.
- [6] Cricket South Africa: CSA Transformation Philosophy and Plan, Johannesburg. 2016. <http://cricket.co.za/item/1943/Transformation>. Date of access: 5 August 2016.
- [7] Desai, A., ed. 2010. *The Race to Transform: Sport in Post-Apartheid South Africa*. Cape Town: HSRC Press.
- [8] Desai, A. 2016. *Reverse Sweep: A Story of South African Cricket Since Apartheid*. Auckland Park: Jacana Media.
- [9] Du Preez, J. 2014. Quotas in Sport: Racially Isolating Ourselves Once More. <http://www.ngopulse.org/article/quotas-sport-racially-isolating-ourselves-once-more> Date of access: 20 December 2016.
- [10] ESPN Cricinfo. 2006. <http://www.espncricinfo.com/england/content/story/270556.html> Date of access: 8 August 2016.
- [11] Farland, D. and Jennings, I. 2007. Cricket and Representivity: The case of Race Quotas in Team Selection in *Sport and Society* 10(5), pp. 818-839.
- [12] Fox, W., Schwella, E. and Wissink, H.F. 1991. *Public Management*. Cape Town: Juta.
- [13] Greenaway, M. 2007. Sports Quotas Out – Stofile. <http://www.iol.co.za/capeargus/sport/sports-quotas-out---stofile-580805c> Date of access: 20 August 2016.
- [14] Hartman, R. 2004. *Ali: The Life of Ali Bacher*. Johannesburg: Penguin.

- [15] International Cricket Council. 2012. ICC Anti-Racism Policy for International Cricket. <https://www.icc-cricket.com/about/integrity/anti-racism> Date of access: 17 December 2016.
- [16] Louw, A.M., 2014. The Return of Racial Quotas in South African Sport. <http://sportsfire.co.za/the-return-of-racial-quotas-in-south-african-sport> Date of access: 8 April 2016.
- [17] Macpherson, W. 2016. Cricket South Africa admit they are powerless to stop England player drain. The Guardian: 12 December. <https://www.theguardian.com/sport/2016/dec/12/south-africa-test-player-drain-english-counties-kolpak-deals> Date of access: 4 April 2016.
- [18] Manthorp, N. 2014. Black Players Conflicted Over New CSA Quotas. <http://mg.co.za/article/2014-09-11-black-players-conflicted-over-new-csa-quotas> . Date of Access: 24 August 2016.
- [19] Mnyanda, S. 2016. Imposing racial quotas is a vital step forward for South African sport. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/apr/29/south-africa-racial-quotas-sport-rugby-springboks-cricket>. Date of access: 25 April 2017.
- [20] Mphahlele, M., 2017. New Minister to Focus on Sport Transformation. <https://www.businesslive.co.za/bd/sport/2017-04-26-new-minister-to-focus-on-sport-transformation/> Date of access: 25 June 2017.
- [21] Molobi, T., 2015. Transformation in Sport: Not much achieved in 21 years. <http://www.citypress.co.za/sport/more-quotas-fewer-quotes> Date of access: 8 August 2016.
- [22] Moonda, F., 2013. CSA Introduce Quotas for Black African Players <http://www.espnricinfo.com/southafrica/content/story/679057.html> Date of access: 16 August 2016.
- [23] Moonda, F., 2016. CSA Punished for Slow Transformation <http://www.espnricinfo.com/southafrica/content/story/1003263.html> Date of access: 16 August 2016.
- [24] Murray, B. and Merrett, C. 2004. Caught Behind: Race and Politics in Springbok Cricket. Johannesburg: Wits University Press.
- [25] Naidoo, L. D. 2008. Theoretical Foundations of Sport Administration: Is Government 'Interference' Justified? *Journal of Business and Management Dynamics*. 2(1), pp.20-31.
- [26] Nyoka, M. 2015. Deliberate Concealment: An Insider's Account of Cricket South Africa and the IPL Bonus Saga. Johannesburg: Picador Africa.
- [27] Osborne, P. 2004. Basil D'Oliveira. Cricket and Conspiracy: The Untold Story. London: Little, Brown.
- [28] Odenadaal, A., 2003. The Story of an African Game. Claremont: David Philip Publishers.
- [29] Odendaal, A. 2010. South Africa are isolated. ESPN Sports Media. <http://www.espnricinfo.com/magazine/content/story/463657.html> Date of access: 28 April 2017.
- [30] Oxford English Dictionary. 2007. Vol.2 6th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [31] Pretorius, W. 2016. Most Black South Africans Oppose Sport Quotas – Survey. <http://www.news24.com/SouthAfrica/News/most-black-south-africans-oppose-sport-quotas-survey-20160531>. Date of access: 17 August 2016.
- [32] South Africa. 1998. The Employment Equity Act 55 of 1998. Pretoria: Government Printers.
- [33] South Africa. 2006. National Sports and Recreation Amendment Bill.
- [34] South Africa. 2015. Eminent Persons Group Transformation Status Report 2014/15.
- [35] Steen, R., 2013. Quotas are Less Black and White than Ever. <http://www.espnricinfo.com/magazine/content/story/681291.html> Date of access: 30 March 2016.
- [36] Taliep, M. S. 2009. Effectiveness of the cricket transformation process in increasing representation and performance of black cricketers at provincial level in South Africa. *South African Journal of Sports Medicine*. 21(4), pp156-162.
- [37] Thomen, C., 2008. Is it Cricket?: An Ethical Evaluation of Race Quotas in Sport. Lambert Academic Publishing. London.
- [38] Vahed, G. H. & Padayachee, V. & Desai, A. (2006). Beyond Apartheid: Race, Transformation and Governance in KwaZulu-Natal Cricket. *Transformation: Critical Perspectives on Southern Africa* 61(1), 63-88.

- [39] Young, J., 2016. Grow Black Protea Cricketers at School Level. <https://mg.co.za/article/2016-04-28-grow-black-protea-cricketers-at-school-level> Date of access: 2 July 2017.